

Title of the case report: Cervical Ectopic Pregnancy in a 40-year-Old Woman: case report

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Abstract

Cervical ectopic pregnancy (CP), a relatively rare disease, accounts for less than 0.1% of ectopic pregnancies. It has a high potential for morbidity and mortality. Prompt intervention is necessary to preserve fertility and avoid the need for a hysterectomy. The difficulties in the diagnosis and treatment of a case of CP are explored. Transvaginal ultrasonography is essential to making the correct diagnosis. To prevent significant complications, including severe hemorrhage and the necessity for a hysterectomy, early identification and treatment are essential. The clinical presentation determines the best course of action. In this case report, we present a case of a 40-year old woman with cervical ectopic pregnancy and go over the management. This case report highlights the rarity of cervical ectopic pregnancy, and how correct diagnosis and swift management would yield a favorable outcome.

Keywords:

Cervix, Cervical Ectopic Pregnancy, ultrasound, etc.

Case

A 40-year-old patient presented to our emergency room with complaints of vaginal bleeding associated with lower abdominal cramps. The patient brought with her pelvic MRI report done at a different center one day before her presentation which showed endocervical canal ballooning with high T2 cystic structure, measuring 1.8 x 1.3 x 1.3 cm with moderate left side hydrosalpinx Figure [1-2]. She did not have any systemic discomfort except for some vaginal spotting for one day before the presentation. Her last menstrual period was 6 weeks ago and lasted for 6 days. The patient's medical history included a laparotomy 5 years ago for a right ovarian Dermoid cyst and a Cesarean section 4 years ago. On pelvic examination, the external cervical os was closed with moderate bleeding. Transvaginal ultrasonography showed an anteverted normal-sized corpus, where no gestational sac was present in the uterine cavity. In the gestational sac with an embryonic pole no fetal heartbeat was seen implanted in the cervical canal and the peritrophoblastic flow was well demonstrated by pelvic color Doppler ultrasonography (Fig. 1). To minimize the bleeding vaginal pack was inserted and Tranexamic acid 1 mg IV was given to the patient. Bleeding improved and the patient was stabilized. A blood sample showed a beta-hCG level of 11,960 mIU/mL, a white blood cell count of 6800/ μ L, hemoglobin 11.7 g/dL, and a platelet count of 301,000/ μ L. The patient received counseling and the options for managing a cervical pregnancy were explained, including the risk related to intraoperative bleeding, which can be unpredictably catastrophic or life-threatening. The patient was admitted to the hospital that same day and was advised of the well-prepared precautions before surgery. The patient agreed to a dilatation and curettage which was performed immediately. The procedure went smoothly under intravenous general anesthesia. A gentle cervical curettage was done followed by insertion of a no. 18 Foleys 'catheter with 50 ml saline used to inflate the cervical canal to control bleeding by tamponade effect (fig 2). Hemostasis was achieved. There was no massive bleeding and the postoperative course was uneventful. Histopathology report confirmed the

presence of chorionic villi and decidual tissue with cervical stroma and glands. The patient was discharged on the 2nd day after cervical catheter removal and advised for 2-week follow-up visits to our outpatient department with serum Beta hCG report. The beta-hCG level after curettage 2 weeks later was 1.9 mIU/mL. Follow-up scan revealed complete resolution.

Figure (1-2): Multisequential multiplanar MRI with IV gadolinium contrast administration show endocervical canal ballooning with high T2 cystic structure, measuring 1.8 x 1.3 x 1.3 cm with moderate left side hydrosalpinx.

Discussion

An ectopic pregnancy that implants into the cervical mucosa below the level of the internal os is known as a cervical ectopic pregnancy. With a reported prevalence of 1 in 1000–95000 pregnancies, they represent less than 1% of all ectopic pregnancies. In 1978, the first report of an ultrasound-detected cervical ectopic pregnancy was published. [1,2]

Ectopic pregnancies in the cervical region have traditionally been treated surgically. Surgery is frequently risky because of the anatomical position of cervical ectopic pregnancies. As a result, a lot of women who experienced this kind of ectopic pregnancy got hysterectomy. Most ectopic pregnancies, including cervical pregnancies, are now discovered sooner, thanks to the improved availability of transvaginal ultrasound scanning facilities and the quick testing of serum human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG). Early detection leads to lower serum hCG levels, greater clinical stability, and the possibility of conservative management for the patient. [3]

The exact etiology and pathophysiology of Cervical ectopic pregnancy is still unknown. However, it has been hypothesized that they could be caused by uterine cavity injury, which prevents the normal implantation of the fetus in the endometrium. When an embryo undergoes nidation in the endocervical canal, a cervical pregnancy results. Instead of the uterine cavity, the fertilized ovum implants itself inside the cervix. It is challenging to discern between a miscarriage and fetal parts in the cervical area unless the fetal heart rate can be determined.[4]

Any compromise in uterine cavity capacity is a significant risk factor that limits endometrial implantation, leading to cervical ectopic pregnancy. [5]

The major risk factors include in vitro fertilization, variant anatomy, fibroids endometrial injury ,uterine curettage , IUCD etc .[5]

Diagnosis and Management

Following a period of amenorrhea, the most typical symptom is vaginal bleeding, which is frequently painless. Occasionally, however, significant bleeding can occur, necessitating surgery to save the patient, as was the case in our first case. Three morphological and histological criteria for the diagnosis of cervical pregnancy, which can be made in a hysterectomy specimen, were proposed by Rubin in 1911. In 1959, Paalman and McElin offered

more clinically useful criteria, which includes, bleeding from the uterus without pain after a period of amenorrhea. A soft, expanded cervix that is at least as large as the fundus and contains all of the fetal tissue securely linked to the endocervix and a slightly opened external cervical os with a closed internal cervical os [6,7] .

Cervical pregnancy can easily be mistaken as a scar pregnancy due to ultrasound characteristics. Pregnancy in the cervical region occurs below the internal os, whereas pregnancy in the scar region occurs above, at the level of the incision on the cesarean scar. Additionally, a continuing abortion is frequently misinterpreted as a cervical pregnancy. The sliding sign, which indicates that when light pressure is applied to the cervix with the probe, the implanted cervical pregnancy does not slide in contrast to the gestational sac of the abortion, is the best technique to tell the two circumstances apart [5]

It can be viewed as a gestational sac inside the uterus' hourglass shape-giving dilated cervix. Internal OS is typically closed. When the gestational sac is positioned excessively low, it can occasionally expand into the lower region of the uterus. The region around the gestational sac exhibits hyperechoic decidual responses. In cases of live cervical ectopic pregnancies, color Doppler imaging can be useful in demonstrating a hypervascularity trophoblastic ring in the cervical region. [5]

The patient's intent to preserve fertility, hemodynamic condition, and gestational age should all be taken into consideration when choosing the appropriate course of treatment, as well as the initial serum hCG level, crown-rump length, and the existence or absence of a fetal heartbeat. [8]

Methotrexate, a folate antagonist, can be administered systemically or directly by injection, and potassium chloride can also be administered directly by injection. Hemorrhage that could be life-

threatening can occur during surgical curettage. Reduce the risk of hemorrhage via preoperative uterine embolization. The preferred course of action is medical therapy in a first-trimester cervical pregnancy with a hemodynamically stable patient who is not bleeding heavily. Misoprostol, mifepristone, and methotrexate have all been used, typically in conjunction with interventional procedures, to medically end a cervical pregnancy.^[5]

Methotrexate is the most efficient medical treatment, whether it is administered systemically in a single-dose or multiple-dose intramuscular regimen, locally via an intra-amniotic injection, or both. When the blood hCG level is greater than 10.000 mIU/mL, the crown-rump length is greater than 10 mm, or a fetal heartbeat is detected, systemic methotrexate treatment frequently fails. In these circumstances, combining therapy with intra-amniotic methotrexate may improve the therapeutic outcome. It is also advised to administer potassium chloride intra-amniotically for feticide or embryocide when there is a heartbeat.^[9,10]

When doing the intra-amniotic injection, some writers indicate favorable results in aspirating and injecting roughly similar volumes into the cavity such that the internal pressure does not change. Excessive bleeding is prevented by this method. Although the methotrexate intra-amniotic injection in our situation was unsuccessful, the surgery was nevertheless uneventful. A fertility-sparing surgery approach could be used with the removal of the trophoblast via curettage/aspiration or surgical hysteroscopy if the prior medical treatment fails or is contraindicated.^[5]

Conclusion

One percent of all ectopic pregnancies are cervical pregnancies, an uncommon kind of ectopic pregnancy. The preferred course of treatment is early diagnosis and medical intervention using systemic or local methotrexate injection. In the event that the pregnancy is disrupted, there may be a significant amount of bleeding, necessitating a hysterectomy to save the patient. A transvaginal ultrasound and a clinical examination confirmed the cervical pregnancy diagnosis.

The most successful medicinal intervention is methotrexate (systemic and/or local). Conservative surgery, such as curettage or surgical hysteroscopy, can be used to remove the trophoblast if methotrexate is ineffective or not recommended. A technique to lessen the bleeding risk before or after conservative surgery may be essential because there is always a high risk of serious hemorrhage that could necessitate a hysterectomy.

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